

SIMILAR AND DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF PROVERBS IN RELATION TO OTHER GENRES OF FOLKLORE

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Abstract: *This article is dedicated to the similarities and differences of proverbs with other genres. In examining the mentality of the Uzbek and English people, the Uzbek and English proverbs can highlight the similarities and differences between the two nations. It is possible to find the equivalent proverbs in both on the same topic. In analyzing lingua-cultural aspects of Uzbek and English proverbs, it is important to note that the language and culture of both peoples are interrelated.*

Keywords: *Proverbs, folklore, equivalency, difference, similarity.*

Proverbs are one of the most important genres of folklore, and today new aspects of linguistics are revealed through the in-depth study of proverbs in comparative linguistics. On the other hand, it is a comparative study of the linguacultural and semantic features of proverbs in English and Uzbek languages and a generalization of their similarities and differences. In particular, the comparative study of Uzbek and English proverbs proves the similarities and differences in the mentality of the peoples, expressing the extent to which the language reflects the cultural and national customs of both peoples.

Proverbs are an international genre by their nature. There is no nation in the world that does not have its own proverbs. Because every nation leaves its life experiences to generations in the form of proverbs. That is why there are many proverbs that are close to each other in terms of content and form in the oral works of different nations.

Proverbs differ from other genres of folklore according to the following specific features:

- The volume of the proverbs will be short and limited;
- Proverbs reflect a broad and deep meaning;
- Folk proverbs are formed in poetic and prose form;
- Proverbs reflect a positive or negative judgment about life events;

- Proverbs summarize a private situation in a person's life from the point of view of the people and life;
- The text of a proverb is a generalized sentence in linguistics;
- It appears and disappears very slowly;
- Proverbs do not choose space and time, they are used in all situations in the same way, they are used in a certain situation;
- The thought expressed in the proverb has been tested in the centuries-old social experience of the people, and the thought expressed in it acquires a universal character;
 - A proverb often has a figurative meaning (metaphorical);
 - Proverb is an international genre by its nature. In the context of the terms that mean it, the meaning of words, advice, wisdom, intelligent words is understood;
 - Proverbs not only express the centuries-old experiences of the people, but also interpret them.

Among the genres of folklore, there are genres such as sayings and riddles, which are close to proverbs in terms of size, external features, and the way they reflect reality. Today we can encounter these problems in the folklore of all nations. We face the same problem in English proverbs as in Uzbek. Like Uzbek folk proverbs, English folk proverbs are sharply distinguished from sayings and riddles by the following features. These are as follows:

- In a proverb, the thought is expressed in the form of a clear, complete conclusion, and a concise judgment. Sayings do not express a complete thought. Although riddles are close to proverbs in form, but the way of reflecting reality, it differs sharply from proverbs mainly by hiding the thought in the form of riddles. Despite the fact that proverbs and riddles serve as one of the most productive genres of folklore, there are similarities and differences between them.

- The finding does not express any suggestion or judgment. Maybe a certain idea, something will be hidden in it. There is no similarity between riddles and proverbs except for formal similarity. The same situation can be observed in English folk proverbs.

For example, "*There is no place like home*". In this proverb, it is expressed that the house where one was born and grew up is better and more valuable than gold.

- The proverb has a complete sentence and a clear conclusion. Or from riddles: "*It's running night and day, but it never runs away*". The riddle asks for something that works day and night, i.e. "clock". In the find, the clockwork is expressed and no judgment or conclusion is shown.

Studying proverbs in English shows that examples of this genre are almost identical in content to proverbs in Uzbek. However, it would not be correct to explain

such a closeness by the fact that one nation adopted a proverb from another nation. In our opinion, it is better to explain such closeness by the similarity of simple way of life, closeness of relationships in people's life and, in general, the same situation in many situations of life. For example:

In Uzbek *"It hurar karvon o'tar .*

In English *"The dogs bark, but caravan goes on".*

Or in English *"When the cat is away, the mice will play"*

We can give the translation of this proverb like: *"O'tning o'limi – itning bayrami"*.

Proverbs are a phenomenon between verbal artistic creation and philosophy, and no one can deny the judgment expressed in them. Because such a judgment, first of all, has been repeatedly tested and confirmed in life experience over the centuries, and then, due to the same characteristic, became the wisdom of history and acquired a motivational essence. Therefore, it has become a common practice for the listeners to accept the thoughts in the proverbs without objection, without any resistance or explanation. There is no doubt that the logic in proverbs is strong and the thought is convincing. Therefore, proverbs can be used anywhere in speech, for any purpose. Nevertheless, proverbs, sayings or riddles are always spoken and listened to in a serious tone compared to other genres of folklore. But in some cases, proverbs can be used in the sense of sarcasm, insult, irony. For example: Long hair and short wit – *Sochi uzun – aqli kalta.*

As we have seen, proverbs are the cultural heritage of people. It reflects all the thoughts, worldviews, lifestyles, character and beliefs of the people. Since each nation has its own characteristics, it does not affect their proverbs. Even though the topics in the articles are similar, their images are unique. These images provide the national color of the articles. although Uzbek and English folk proverbs differ sharply from other genres of folklore with many characteristics, many of them are the product of creation, anonymous creation, oral life, wide variation and originality with its popularity, it has commonalities with all genres of folklore. And here, the study of their different aspects shows that proverbs have special characteristics from other genres. This embodies proverbs as a unique and special genre that should be studied in folklore.

REFERENCES:

1. Karamatova K.M., Karamatov H.S. Proverbs–Maqollar– Пословицы.-Т.: Mehnat, –2000. –398 b.
2. Korunets I.V. Theory and Practice of Translating. - Vinnytsia: Nova Knyga, 2001. –265p.
3. Marvin, D.E. Antiquity of Proverbs. - New York and London: G.P Putnam Sons, 1922. –103 p.
4. Madayev O., Sobitova T. Xalq og‘zaki poetik ijodi. – T.: Sharq, 2010.
5. Meider, W. Dundes, A. The Wisdom of Many: Essays on the Proverb. - New York: Garland, 1995. –340p
6. Mirzayev T., Musokulov A., Sarimsakov B. Uzbek folkproverbs. - T. : Sharq, 2005. –408 p.
7. Mollanazar, H. Principles and methodology of translation. - Tehran: SAMT, 2001.– 115p.
8. Taylor A. The Proverb. –Harvard University Press, 1995. –234 p.
9. Trench, C.R. On the Lessons in Proverbs. -New York: Redfield, 2005.
10. <http://www.phrases.org.uk/meanings/proverbs.html>
11. <http://www.thesaurus.com/browse/proverb>
12. <http://www.cogweb.ucla.edu/Discourse/Proverbs/English.html>.
13. http://www.executableoutlines.com/pdf/pr2_so.pdf